

EIC User Group Newsletter

March 2020

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NEWS

- Due to the Covid-19 outbreak, the [first “Yellow Report” workshop](#) at Temple Univ. (Philadelphia-USA) could be held on March 19-21 only in **“remote mode”**. Despite this, the workshop was successfully run through all its schedule, with the plenary session of Thursday morning sometimes **exceeding 200 simultaneous connections**. The other sessions were organized by the Conveners of the Physics and Detector Working Groups (WG), alternating **parallel sessions** with single presentations to **joint sessions** for discussion. On Friday afternoon, **plenary sessions** were organized for discussing common topics and, in particular, the issue of **detector complementarity**. Finally, the plenary session of Saturday morning included the **summary from each WG** and a discussion on the framework set up by the Software WG. The workshop was ended with a discussion on the **internationalization of the EIC project**, specifically in view of the work needed towards the next step of the DOE CD1 approval. All material can be found at the [Indico agenda](#). Several **plenary sessions** were also **recorded**. The link will be sent out through the EICUG mailing list.
- In the [“Yellow Report” menu of the EICUG web page](#), one can find the **calendar** of the other scheduled **“Yellow Report” workshops**:
 2. 22-24 May 2020, Univ. and INFN - Pavia - Pavia (Italy)
 3. 17-19 September 2020, CUA - Washington D.C. (USA)
 4. 19-21 November 2020, UCB - Berkeley (USA)Because of the Covid-19 outbreak, the **workshop 2.** foreseen in Pavia will be held **only remotely**.

- A new **Charter Committee** is in place to update the EICUG Charter for the next phase of the EICUG after the DOE CD0. The Committee is **formed** by
 - * John Arrington (Argonne Nat. Lab. - US)
 - * Will Brooks (USM Valparaiso, Chile)
 - * Olga Evdokimov (Univ. of Illinois, Chicago - US)
 - * Yuji Goto (RIKEN, Japan)
 - * Barbara Jacak (LBNL & Univ. California at Berkeley - US)
 - * Richard Milner (MIT - US) (Co-chair)
 - * Marco Radici (INFN Pavia, Italy)
 - * Franck Sabatiè (Saclay, France) (Co-chair)
 - * Sevil Salur (Univ. Rutgers - US)
 - * Daria Sokhan (Univ. Glasgow, UK)

NEWS from the ELECTION & NOMINATION COMMITTEE

- The Committee has started to work on the upcoming election for the office of **International Representative** on the EICUG Steering Committee.
- The new term will start on **July 1st, 2020**. Yuji Goto has agreed to continue in his present term until June 30th, 2020.
- The nomination and election **process will start in April 2020**.

NEWS from the CONFERENCE & TALKS COMMITTEE

- Because of the Covid-19 outbreak, the **schedule** of next workshops of interest for the EICUG has been **drastically modified**: many events have been **postponed** (sometimes with tentative dates) or **cancelled** at all. At present, **all talks** related to the EIC have been **assigned except** for the IWHSS workshop in Trieste and the ICHEP in Prague (see below): no details are given on the corresponding web page about possible delays or cancellation.

- In any case, for consulting the list of **open EICUG talks** see <http://www.eicug.org/web/events/open> . For a list of **previous EICUG talks** see <http://www.eicug.org/web/events/previous> (often including also a link to the presentation). If you wish to recommend a candidate, including yourself, or if in general you wish to suggest new speakers (including yourself) to be considered for future invitations, please contact the Conference & Talks Committee at eicug-talks@eicug.org . Here, you can find also the general [talks guidelines](#) .

NEWS from the SOFTWARE WORKING GROUP

- The EICUG Software Working Group is working on physics and detector simulations that enable for the Yellow Report Initiative a quantitative assessment of the measurement capabilities of the EIC detector(s) and their physics impact. The common simulation tools and workflow environment being setup allow the EICUG to pursue Yellow Report studies in a manner that is accessible, consistent, and reproducible to the EICUG as a whole.
- **Summaries** of the announcements will be shared on eicug-users@eicug.org The introduction to **JupyterLab** as a collaborative workspace for Yellow Report Initiative and the **tutorials** for fast and detector full simulations are available on the YouTube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCXc9WfDKdlLXoZMGrotkf7w>
- On **Monday March 30**, 11:00 am (EDT), there will be a **Q.&A. session** with Chris Pinkenburg (BNL), David Lawrence (JLAB), Dmitry Romanov (JLAB), and Kolja Kauder (BNL). You will be able to join via BlueJeans: <https://bluejeans.com/920347364>
- The **next tutorial** will be on **Thursday, April 9** (EDT). Dmitry Romanov (JLAB) and Kolja Kauder (BNL) will give an advanced tutorial on fast simulations based on the feedback and requests of the last months. For more detailed information, see the [EIC Software web page](#).

NEWS from the PHYSICS WORKING GROUP CONVENERS

- The Yellow Report activities of the **Physics Working Group (PWG)** are in full swing now. The PWG is organized in **five sub-groups**:
 - * Inclusive reactions
 - * Semi-inclusive processes
 - * Jets & Heavy Quarks
 - * Exclusive reactions
 - * Diffraction & Forward tagging.

They are led by co-conveners and rely on enthusiastic efforts of the EICUG community members who have volunteered to take part in this critical effort. You can find **more details** on the organizational structure (or sign-up for ongoing efforts!) at: <http://www.eicug.org/web/content/yellow-report-physics-working-group> .

The **PWG** had set the following **goals** for the **1st Yellow Report meeting**:

- * Review prior work related to the detector requirements
 - * Converge on a set of important and representative measurements for each group
 - * Develop in detail further efforts towards Yellow Report goals
- Despite its online format, the meeting was a very intense and productive event, and significant progress has been made towards these goals (for details, see the **summaries** of each PWG **sub-group** at [Indico agenda](#)). The joint discussions with the Detector WG (DWG) during the meeting have further helped us in shaping the next stage of the exercise and fine-tuning the work plan towards the next 2nd Yellow Report workshop.
- In short, the anticipated **workflow** is as follows:
 - * For the representative physics measurements, start by breaking down physics deliverables into “**physics objects**” (**PO**) [electron, hadron (ID/noID), muon, jet] to map out **relevant kinematics** for each PO
 - * Cross-check PO maps across physics subgroups to determine the most **demanding constraints** in terms of detector design; resolve overlaps.
 - * Focus on fast **simulations** for the most demanding measurements first; determine the optimal/acceptable detector performance; confirm/check resulting **impact** on the rest of the measurements.

- As has been reported in this meeting, some studies have already progressed to the point of specific detector requirements. For others, more simulation work is now being initiated in coordination with the DWG. We will next report on the progress and developments at the next meeting.

NEWS from the DETECTOR WORKING GROUP CONVENERS

- The Conveners of the Detector WG (DWG) found the workshop highly informative (in particular, the plenary session on Thursday morning) and helpful to the planning of the next activities also because of the large attendance and lively discussions.
- The DWG sessions consisted of **six subgroups** (tracking, particle ID, calorimetry, far forward/IR integration/ancillary/polarimetry/luminosity, DAQ/electronics, and central detector/magnet) split over **four parallel session blocks** on Thursday afternoon and Friday morning. The sessions were organized by the sub-conveners listed below. The typical format of the sessions included **presentations of the technologies** both considered by the R&D Consortia and new, as well as cross-cutting presentations on **physics simulations and requirements**, and discussions of the path forward. In particular, each subgroup was asked to develop a strategy to meet the **overall goal** of presenting initial detector concepts and implications for physics measurements at the **next Yellow Report Workshop**. The sessions were well attended and good progress was made. It is well evident that all detector subgroups have started their activities moving in the right direction, even if the advancement level is currently not uniform because of different initial conditions. The DWG conveners are particularly pleased with the **wide attendance** and the dedication of the participants. They have collected very valuable feedback to steer the overall activity towards the common YR goals.

- Furthermore, the DWG had a **plenary session** on complementary detectors and a joint session with the PWG on Friday afternoon. The **complementary detector** session featured an introduction talk and a discussion with the audience. The **joint session** was co-organized by the **DWG+PWG** Conveners and consisted of the debate of four main questions posed by the two groups to each other to **streamline efforts** and optimize interactions among all working group contributors. Both sessions were well attended and provided important information for the planning of future activities. **Globally**, the DWG Conveners regard the workshop as a **successful event** beyond their expectation. They believe that it depicts promising perspectives for the YR initiative.
- **DWG session conveners:**
 - * *Tracking*: Kondo Gnanvo (UVA), Leo Greiner (LBNL), Annalisa Mastroserio (INFN)
 - * *Particle ID*: Tom Hemmick (SBU), Patrizia Rossi (JLab)
 - * *DAQ/Electronics*: Andrea Celentano (INFN), Damien Neyret (CEA Saclay)
 - * *Calorimetry*: Vladimir Berdnikov (CUA), Eugene Chudakov (JLab)
 - * *Far-forward/IR integration/polarimetry/ancillary/luminosity*: Alexander Jentsch (BNL), Michael Murray (Kansas), Yulia Furletova (JLab), Elke Aschenauer (BNL), Dave Gaskell (JLab)
 - * *Central detector/Integration and Magnet*: William Brooks (UTF-SM), Alexander Kiselev (BNL)
 - * *Detector Complementarity*: Elke Aschenauer (BNL)

NEWS from the INSTITUTIONAL BOARD

- The **EICUG** currently stands at **1055 members**, from **216 institutions** in 31 countries. Theory members are approximately 26%, experimentalists 60%, experts in accelerators 14%.

This is a pie chart illustrating how the 216 EICUG Institutions are split into the 6 world regions.

- Since February 2020, **five new Institutions** have joined the EICUG:
 - * Beijing Normal University (China)
 - * T. Kosciuszko Krakow University of Technology (Poland)
 - * Jazan University (Saudi Arabia)
 - * Institute of Mathematical Sciences (India)
 - * Vanderbilt University (US)

RECENT WORKSHOPS/MEETINGS of INTEREST

See also <http://www.eicug.org/web/events/previous> (includes also links to some presentations)

Those events labeled by were held with on-line only format.

[CPAD Instrumentation Frontier Workshop](#), Madison (WI - USA), 8-10 December 2019

[EIC Physics and Detector Conceptual Developments kick-off meeting](#), MIT - Boston (MA - USA), 12-13 December 2019

[International workshop on QCD with EIC \(QEIC\)](#), Bombay (India), 4-7 January 2020

[Exploring QCD with light nuclei at EIC](#), Stony Brook (NY - US), 21-24 January 2020

[EIC Detector R&D Committee Meeting](#), Upton (NY - US), 30-31 January 2020

[Correlations in Partonic and Hadronic Interactions \(CPHI-2020\)](#), CERN-Geneva (Switzerland), 3-7 February 2020

[2020 Santa Fe Jets and Heavy Flavor Workshop](#), Santa Fe (NM - US), 3-5 February 2020

[Winter Workshop on Nuclear Dynamics](#), Puerto Vallarta (Mexico), 1-7 March 2020

[A.I. for Nuclear Physics Workshop](#), Jefferson Lab - Newport News (VA-US), 3-6 March 2020

[KEK Workshop on Femtotechnologies by quantum computers 2020](#), Tsukuba (Japan), 7 March 2020

[1st EIC Physics and Detector Conceptual Development Workshop](#), Philadelphia (MD-US), 19-21 March 2020

UPCOMING WORKSHOPS/MEETINGS of INTEREST

See also <http://www.eicug.org/web/events/upcoming> and <http://cnr2.kent.edu/~manley/BRAGmeetings.html>

The events labeled by are being considered to be held with on-line only format.

[DIS 2020](#), Brooklyn (NY- USA), 23-27 March 2020 **Cancelled**

[Rencontres de Moriond, QCD and high-energy interactions](#), La Thuile (Italy), 28 March - 4 April 2020 **Cancelled**

[Jet observables at an Electron Ion Collider](#), Upton (NY - US), 15-17 April 2020 **Cancelled**

[QCD Evolution 2020](#), Los Angeles (CA - US), 27 April - 1 May 2020 **Cancelled**

[Origin of the Visible Universe: Unraveling the Proton Mass \(INT-20-77W\)](#), INT Seattle (WA - US), 4 - 8 May 2020 **Postponed**

[The 17th International Workshop on Hadron Structure and Spectroscopy](#), Trieste (Italy), 17-22 May 2020 **Postponed**

[2nd EIC Physics and Detector Conceptual Development Workshop](#), Pavia (Italy), 22-24 May 2020

[Transversity 2020](#), Pavia (Italy), 25-29 May 2020 **Postponed**

[Joint GlueX-PANDA-EIC Workshop on Machine Learning for Particle Physics Experiments](#), Darmstadt (Germany), 25-29 May 2020 **Postponed**

[Hard Probes](#), Austin (TX - USA), 1-6 June 2020 **Postponed** /

[Tomography of light nuclei at an EIC](#), ECT*-Trento (Italy), 15-19 June 2020

[LXX International Conference NUCLEUS-2020](#), Saint Petersburg (Russia), 26-30 June 2020 **Postponed**

[Light-Cone 2020](#), Jeju (Korea), 29 June - 4 July 2020 **Postponed** : 14-18 Dec. 2020

[9th International Conference on New Frontiers in Physics \(ICNFP 2020\)](#),
Kolymbari (Crete - Greece), 27 July - 7 August 2020

[40th International Conference on High Energy Physics \(ICHEP 2020\)](#),
Prague (Czech Republic), 30 July - 5 August 2020

[EIC Users Group Meeting 2020](#), Miami (F - USA), 3-7 August 2020

[Photonuclear Gordon Conference](#), Holderness (NH - USA), 9-14 August
2020 **Cancelled**

[22nd International Conference on Particles and Nuclei \(PANIC2020\)](#),
Lisbon (Portugal), 31 August - 4 September 2020

[24th International Spin Symposium SPIN2020](#), Matsue (Japan), 20-25
September 2020

[Baryon 2020](#), Sevilla (Spain), 22-25 September 2020

[New Physics Phenomena - Hadronic Contributions to New Physics
Searches](#), Crete (Greece), 24-30 September 2020

[Lepton-Photon 2021](#), Manchester (UK), 9-14 August 2021

Quarks and Nucleon Physics QNP 2021, Bonn (Germany), 20-24
September 2021